

Understanding perceived tranquillity in urban Woonerf streets: case studies in two Dutch cities

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1. Introduction

Woonerf streets in the Netherlands are designed as shared spaces that reduce vehicle dominance and promote human-centred environments. While such designs are expected to foster tranquillity, current urban planning models often rely on noise exposure levels or land-use proxies to predict perceived tranquillity.

This study investigated whether these predicted values align with people's actual experiences. By comparing field-based soundscape assessments with GIS-derived indices, we explored how acoustic perception varies across neighbourhoods.

Our aim was to assess the reliability of existing predictive tools and advocate for more perceptually grounded approaches to urban soundscape evaluation and planning.

2. Methodology

Predicted Tranquillity = $f(\text{LA}_{\text{eq}}, \text{Green View Index (GVI)}, \text{Natural-Cultural Factors (NCF)})$.

- 61 Woonerf streets (Groningen [31], Leeuwarden [30])
- 52 georeferenced sampling locations
- 208 street-level photographs
- 150 is-situ sound level measurements
- 3,000 questionnaires administered
- 403 responses (response rate: 13.4%)

➔ Data collection period: 1 - 30 November 2022 (8-11:00 am)

3. Results

3.1 Relationship between age and perceived tranquillity

Fig.1: Average perceived tranquillity rating among the 13 neighbourhoods in Groningen and Leeuwarden with N ≥ 20

Significant variations in perceived tranquillity across different age groups. Respondents aged **56–65** reported higher tranquillity levels compared to younger cohorts, particularly those under 35. These differences were statistically significant, indicating that age is a meaningful factor influencing tranquillity perception in urban Woonerf streets.

3.2 Spatial variability of NCF

Fig.2: NCF Percentage simulated within the Woonerf streets in (a) Groningen and (b) Leeuwarden

- NCF: **positive** predictor of tranquillity in the TRAPT model.
- **No significant** NCF difference between Groningen and Leeuwarden.
- **Limited spatial variation** may reduce NCF's explanatory power.

Fig.3: Average predicted and perceived TR of (a) 61 Woonerf streets in Groningen and Leeuwarden, (b) 51 Woonerf streets in Groningen and Leeuwarden (N ≥ 20), (c) 30 Woonerf streets in Leeuwarden (N ≥ 20), and (d) 31 Woonerf streets in Groningen (N ≥ 20).

Original TRAPT equation:

$$TR = a + b \cdot NCF - c \cdot LA_{\text{eq}} + MF$$

Adjusted TRAPT equation in this study:

$$TR = 10.55 + 0.041 \cdot NCF - 0.146 \cdot LA_{\text{eq}}$$

4. Key Takeaways

- The **adjusted TRAPT model** helps estimate tranquillity in dense urban settings using **LAeq** and **NCF**.
- **NCF** increased tranquillity scores, but limited spatial variation reduced predictive power.
- **Age and neighbourhood context** showed stronger effects on perception than model variables alone.

➔ **Future work:** explore spatial regression to account for contextual variation & spatial dependence in tranquillity perception.

